

Vulnerability prediction using pre-trained models: An empirical evaluation

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Abstract—The rise of Large Language Models (LLMs) has provided new directions for addressing downstream text classification tasks, such as vulnerability prediction, where segments of the source code are classified as vulnerable or not. Several recent studies have employed transfer learning in order to enhance vulnerability prediction taking advantage of the prior knowledge of the pre-trained LLMs. In the current study, different Transformer-based pre-trained LLMs are examined and evaluated with respect to their capacity to predict vulnerable software components. In particular, we fine-tune BERT, GPT-2, and T5 models, as well as their code-oriented variants namely CodeBERT, CodeGPT, and CodeT5 respectively. Subsequently, we assess their performance and we conduct an empirical comparison between them to identify the models that are the most accurate ones in vulnerability prediction.

Index Terms—Software security, Vulnerability prediction, Transfer learning, Large language models, Transformer

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, software security is considered a significant characteristic of the software development life-cycle, based on the ISO/IEC 25010 International Standard on Software Quality [1]. A major concern of the software community from the aspect of software security is the identification and mitigation of the software vulnerabilities that reside in the source code. Those vulnerabilities are weaknesses in software systems, which can be exploited by external threats [2]. Their identification is considered crucial for the deployment of any software product. A technique capable of predicting hotspots (e.g., files, classes, methods, etc.) of a software product that contains vulnerabilities is Vulnerability Prediction (VP). Software enterprises can benefit from such a mechanism by allocating their limited time and testing effort to potentially vulnerable components.

Vulnerability prediction is commonly performed through Machine Learning (ML) algorithms utilizing software attributes as input. The two largest categories of Vulnerability Prediction Models (VPMs) are based either on code metrics or text mining. Software metrics-based techniques utilize metrics like complexity and coupling that can be retrieved using static code analyzers and can be used as features to train an ML model [3], [4]. On the other hand, text mining approaches receive the text of the source code as input and through ML models, they identify textual vulnerable patterns in the

source code [5]–[7]. There are studies that have compared the performance of software metrics-based and text mining-based models demonstrating important benefits from the text mining approaches [8], [9].

Initially, text mining-based studies in VP employed the Bag of Words (BoW) technique, which represents the source code as a set of words. In BoW, each word is accompanied by the number or the frequency of its appearances in the analyzed software component and it is considered as a feature for an ML classifier [5]. Then researchers started to represent the source code as token sequences. In this approach, deep learning models are utilized to recognize vulnerable patterns in the sequences of source code tokens [10], [11]. To enhance the predictability of the models, the tokens are transformed into numerical vectors by using word embedding methods such as word2vec [12] and fastText [13]. Later, researchers represented the source code with text-rich graphs (e.g., Abstract Syntax Trees, Code Properties Graphs, etc.) [14].

Recent text mining-based studies adopted Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques to perform vulnerability prediction, taking advantage of the innovative Transformer architecture [15]. In particular, they applied transfer learning utilizing Transformer-based [15] Large Language Models (LLMs) [16], [17], which are pre-trained on large generic datasets for their primary tasks, such as next word prediction or prediction of masked tokens [15], [18]. These models have managed to learn the syntax and semantics of thousands of tokens in several different contexts. Hence, in the VP field, researchers can fine-tune them to adjust their deep language knowledge to the downstream task of vulnerability prediction.

However, the wide variety of LLMs that have already been proposed in the literature on NLP and the different characteristics and specialties of each raise questions about which ones are the most suitable and competent for code analysis and in particular for the downstream task of VP. For instance, there are LLMs focused on natural language (NL) understanding whereas others have been designed for source code analysis. Moreover, some LLMs utilize both the encoder and decoder parts of the Transformer architecture whereas some others use only the encoder or the decoder part.

The objective of this study is to identify the optimal choice among a variety of pre-trained Transformer-based models in the downstream task of VP, showcasing any differences in their

performance. To this end, our study aims to assist researchers in their future endeavors to use transfer learning for VP, providing them implications on which of the models found in the related literature are the most appropriate ones for the VP objective. For this purpose, we fine-tune six LLMs on a labeled vulnerability-related dataset of Python source code. These are the following models:

- Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) [19]
- Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) [18], [20]
- Text-To-Text Transfer Transformer (T5) [21]
- CodeBERT [22]
- CodeGPT [23]
- CodeT5 [24]

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II summarizes state-of-the-art approaches in the VP field, focusing on text mining-based methods. Section III details the methodology of our study, while Section IV presents the evaluation results. Finally, Section V concludes the study and suggests future research directions.

II. RELATED WORK

The main Vulnerability Prediction Models (VPMs) in the literature predominantly use machine learning (ML) approaches based on software metrics (e.g., [3]) or text mining (e.g., [5]), with text mining approaches having demonstrated the most promising results [25]. Early work in text mining-based VP focused on the Bag of Words (BoW) technique [5], [8]. Later studies moved towards more complex techniques, particularly deep learning (DL) models like Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), which process the source code as large sequences of tokens [10], [14], aiming to encode both syntactic and semantic patterns from source code. Techniques like word2vec [10] and fastText [26] have been used to create embedding vectors for tokens, with studies indicating that models using these embeddings, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), outperform traditional methods in accuracy [11].

The superiority of the text mining-based approaches and the increased preference of the research community in the VP domain to these methods was highlighted by a recent systematic mapping study [25], which also noted an increasing interest in Transformer-based models. Transformer-based models like BERT, CodeBERT, and RoBERTa [27]–[31] have demonstrated promising results in VP, indicating high capacity in encoding complex vulnerability patterns. For instance, models like VulDeBERT [29] and VulBERTa [27] fine-tuned on code data have outperformed previous state-of-the-art methods like VulDeePecker [10]. Studies like Fu et al. [31] and Zhang et al. [30] have also highlighted the efficacy of Transformer-based models in vulnerability prediction, even at a granular level like line-level predictions.

Although LLMs have already been studied in the VP literature with a number of LLM-based VPMs having been proposed, the choice of the optimal Transformer variant (e.g., encoder-only, decoder-only, or encoder-decoder architectures) and the specific training configurations for the task of VP

remain subjects of investigation. To this end, this study contributes by empirically comparing several Transformer variants, considering encoder-only (e.g., BERT), decoder-only (e.g. GPT), and encoder-decoder (e.g., T5) model architectures, and their code-specific counterparts (CodeBERT, CodeGPT-2, and CodeT5), fine-tuned on a Python-based vulnerability dataset. To ensure fair comparison we adopt the same preprocessing and evaluation process for all the studied models. We present our observations regarding the role of the encoder and decoder parts as well as the role of the size of the models, providing useful implications to researchers on which models they need to pay more attention to in the future. Moreover, we provide replication material in order to enhance the reproducibility of our study [32].

III. STUDY DESIGN

This section describes the overall methodology that we followed in order to fine-tune several pre-trained models to perform vulnerability prediction (VP). We trained BERT, GPT-2, T5, as well as CodeBERT, CodeGPT-2, and CodeT5 using a real-world dataset retrieved by commits on GitHub projects.

A. Dataset

For fine-tuning and evaluating the examined models, we used a dataset that consists of source code files written in Python programming language. This dataset is an extension of the dataset presented by Bagheri et al. [16], who used a version control system as a data source for collecting source code components. Specifically, they used GitHub since it has a high number of software projects. To create a labeled dataset, i.e., a dataset of files signed with a label that declares if they are vulnerable or not, they scanned the commit messages in Python GitHub projects. In particular, they searched for commits, which contain vulnerability-fixing keywords in the commit message. They gathered a large number of Python source files included in such commits. The version of each file before the vulnerability-fixing commit (i.e., parent version) is considered vulnerable, since it contains the vulnerability that required a patch, whereas the version of the file in the vulnerability-fixing commit is considered non-vulnerable.

However, in their study, Bagheri et al. [16] utilized only the fragment of the diff file, which contains the difference between the vulnerable and the fixed version, and they proposed models to separate the "bad" and the "good" parts of a file. In the current study, we extend their dataset by collecting clean (i.e., non-vulnerable) versions from GitHub. For this purpose, we retrieved files from the latest version of the dataset's GitHub repositories, since the latest versions are the safest versions that can be considered non-vulnerable because no vulnerabilities have yet been reported for them. Hence, we can construct models to perform vulnerability prediction at the file-level of granularity. Overall, the extended dataset contains 4,184 Python files, 3,186 of which are considered vulnerable and 998 are considered neutral (i.e., non-vulnerable).

Before training the VPMs, we pre-processed the dataset into sequences of tokens. Initially, we removed comments

and import commands. Subsequently, we replaced numeric constants (e.g., integers, floats, etc.) and String literals with two unique identifiers ("numId\$" and "strId\$") in order to make the sequences more generic. We also dropped empty lines, and finally, we converted the source code of each file into a list of tokens preserving the order of tokens. The tokenized dataset is available online for replication [32].

B. Implementation Strategy

This section describes the Large Language Models (LLMs) that we have included in our study as well as the methodology that we have followed to fine-tune these models to perform vulnerability prediction (VP). All the examined models, which are based on the Transformer architecture, have been pre-trained on a large corpus of textual data for a specific task.

1) *Models Characteristics*: To begin with, the BERT model presented by Google AI¹ is pre-trained on the Masked Language Modeling (MLM) objective. Before being fed into the neural network, 15 % of each sequence of tokens is replaced with a masked token. Then the model aims at predicting the original value of the masked tokens, based on the rest non-masked tokens. This way, BERT learns a bidirectional representation of the sentences [19]. In a replication study of BERT, Liu et al. [33] observed that BERT was significantly under-trained, and therefore, they proposed a robustly optimized pre-training approach, called RoBERTa.

A RoBERTa-based model called CodeBERT, which was presented by Microsoft², is the examined BERT variant that is not pre-trained solely on the English natural language, but on natural language and programming language pairs from 6 programming languages. In particular, it has been trained on bimodal data that include function-level natural language documentations and source code. During the pre-training phase, CodeBERT learns general-purpose representations, which can support tasks that need both natural and programming languages, such as natural language code search and code documentation generation [22].

A similar but different to BERT Transformer-based architecture is the Generative pre-trained transformer (GPT) [18] that was developed by OpenAI³. GPT is not pre-trained on the MLM objective but on predicting the next word in a sentence based on the context provided by the preceding words. It is more suitable for text generation tasks such as questioning-answering and content creation, but it can be fine-tuned for several NLP purposes including text classification, as well. In this study, we utilize the GPT-2 version of the GPT, which is the latest open-source version. It has no major architectural differences in contrast with the first GPT version, but it is much larger in terms of trainable parameters, and also it has been trained on a much larger dataset. Hence, it is considered to have a better language understanding.

Lu et al. introduced CodeGPT-2 [23], a variant of GPT-2. It was pre-trained using programming language data obtained

from the Java and Python subsets of the CodeSearchNet⁴ dataset. It was specifically designed using prior knowledge of programming languages, although it retains the same Transformer decoder-only architecture and the next-token prediction objective as GPT-2. The utility of CodeGPT-2 in software development and code understanding activities can be increased by its fine-tuning for a variety of coding tasks, including code completion, code summarization, and error detection [23].

Google AI has released another Transformer-based pre-trained language model named T5 [21]. T5 is an encoder-decoder model pre-trained on a combination of unsupervised and supervised tasks, where each task is converted into a text-to-text format. Using a large dataset, spans of text are masked during pre-training and the model learns to predict these missing spans. This versatile approach allows T5 to be fine-tuned for various specific NLP tasks, achieving strong performance across numerous benchmarks [21].

Finally, Wang et al. provided CodeT5 [24] by training the T5 model on the semantics of code using identifiers provided by developers. CodeT5 uses the Text-To-Text Transfer Transformer framework, which has been pre-trained in a variety of programming languages from the CodeSearchNet dataset. By leveraging the encoder and decoder parts of T5, this model performs well on a variety of code interpretation and generation tasks, including code summarization, code generation, code translation, and code completion [24].

For all the aforementioned models, we utilize the implementations that are provided by Hugging Face. More specifically, for BERT we use the *bert-base* model, which has 12 layers, 768 hidden size, 12 attention heads in each attention block [15], and 110 millions (M) parameters. For CodeBERT, we choose the *codebert-base-mlm* version, which has the same architecture with *roberta-base*. Specifically, it is a slight differentiation of the BERT architecture with 125M parameters. Regarding GPT-2, we use the *gpt2* model with 12 layers, 768 hidden size, 12 attention heads, and 124M parameters. Similarly, CodeGPT-2 consists of 12 layers, 768 hidden size, 12 attention heads, and 124M trainable parameters. Finally, for T5 and CodeT5 models that employ both the encoder and the decoder parts of the Transformer architecture, we utilize the *t5-base* and *codet5-base* implementations respectively, which have nearly 220M trainable weights. They also contain 12 layers for both the encoder and the decoder (i.e., 24 in total), 768 hidden size, and 12 attention heads in each attention block. All the aforementioned statistics are summarized in Table I.

2) *Methodology*: For the construction of the aforementioned models, we followed a well-defined approach consisting of three phases: (1) pre-training, (2) fine-tuning, and (3) execution. The pre-training has been implemented by each model provider. During pre-training, a large textual dataset is tokenized in a format suitable for each Transformer-based model. Then it is fed to the model, which learns a specific objective (e.g., masked word prediction, next word prediction, etc.) in an unsupervised manner. This way, the trainable

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Google_AI

²<https://github.com/microsoft/CodeBERT>

³<https://openai.com/>

⁴https://huggingface.co/datasets/code_search_net

TABLE I
THE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PRE-TRAINED MODELS CONSIDERED IN THE STUDY

Model	Version	Layers	Hidden Size	Attention heads	Parameters
BERT	<i>bert-base-uncased</i>	12	768	12	110M
CodeBERT	<i>codebert-base-mlm</i>	12	768	12	125M
GPT-2	<i>gpt2</i>	12	768	12	124M
CodeGPT-2	<i>CodeGPT-small-py</i>	12	768	12	124M
T5	<i>t5-base</i>	24	768	12	220M
codeT5	<i>codet5-base</i>	24	768	12	220M

weights of the model have been trained to understand natural language and there have been produced context-aware word embedding vectors, which encode the context of the words. In this study, we receive pre-trained models and we implement the fine-tuning and the execution steps for VP.

During fine-tuning, the training dataset described in Section III-A is utilized. Each Python file with source code is pre-processed (see Section III-A) and is tokenized. For the tokenization of the data, we use the tokenizer that corresponds to each model and is provided by Hugging Face. After applying such a tokenizer, the dataset is transformed into a form that contains only words included in each model’s vocabulary as well as some special tokens. For instance, when using BERT for sequence classification, we need a special classification token (i.e., [CLS]) to be placed at the beginning of each sequence, and another special token (i.e., [SEP]) to separate the sequences. Subsequently, the tokenized sequences along with their corresponding labels are going to be fed to our classifier which consists of the already trained Transformer-based model and a newly added classification layer (i.e., head).

This way, we train, in a supervised manner, the classification layer to separate the vulnerable from the non-vulnerable sequences. Simultaneously, the weights of the Transformer are also updated in order to be adjusted to the needs of the specific classification task. During fine-tuning, the hyperparameters that need to be determined are (1) the number of epochs, (2) the learning rate, (3) the optimizer, (4) the loss function, and (5) the max length of the sequences. For the selection of the first four, we applied several values to each one in order to achieve optimal efficiency in the validation data (see Section III-C), while for the max length, we used the maximum length of the sequences of tokens in the dataset that can be processed by these Transformer-based models.

In particular, for each examined model, we used its pre-trained Transformer-based architecture along with an additional classification head and we trained it using a learning rate equal to 0.00002. For GPT-based models, a linear scheduler was also applied. For the gradient descent’s optimization, we leveraged the Weighted Adam (AdamW) [34] for the BERT and T5-based models, and simple Adam [35] in the case of GPT models. For the selection of the epochs number, we applied the Early Stopping technique. In addition, the maximum length was configured equal to 512, which is the maximum input size that those models can receive. While the text data were encoded using the corresponding tokenizers, zero padding was used to ensure constant sequence length, and

the truncation technique was used to truncate sequences that were longer than the allowed length. Finally, the loss function was the Cross-Entropy loss [36] in every case.

In the execution phase, after fine-tuning the optimized Transformer-based classifiers for the objective of VP, we can use them as our vulnerability predictors in order to assess new Python files and classify them as vulnerable or not.

C. Evaluation Scheme

For evaluating the fine-tuned models, we divided the dataset into three sets: training, validation, and testing. The validation set was used to select optimal hyperparameters, after which the selected model was trained on the training set and evaluated on the testing set (i.e., unseen data). This approach prevents data bias in model development.

To measure the predictive performance of DL classification models, we used common evaluation metrics, including True Positives (TP), True Negatives (TN), False Positives (FP), and False Negatives (FN). We focused on recall, as it indicates how many actual vulnerabilities are predicted, while precision, which relates to the number of FPs, is also crucial. Therefore, metrics like F_1 -score and F_2 -score, which combine both precision and recall, are most suitable. We chose F_2 -score as our main evaluation metric since it emphasizes recall slightly more than F_1 -score.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of our comparative study among the Transformer-based models, after fine-tuning them on the downstream task of VP. The experiments took place on the CUDA parallel computing platform. To enhance the reproducibility of the experiments, we provide our scripts online [32]. All the reported results are the outcome of applying the fine-tuned LLMs on the testing set of the dataset (see Section III-C) along with some state-of-the-art text mining-based approaches. In Table II, we present the outcome of our evaluation scheme. More specifically, Table II provides the values of accuracy, precision, recall, F_1 -score, and F_2 -score, with the latter to be considered as the most critical metric, as explained in Section III-C.

First, Table II presents the superiority of the LLM-based VPMS over three state-of-the-art text mining-based approaches. In particular, we compare the fine-tuned LLMs to (i) BoW, (ii) Term Frequency–Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF), which is a BoW variant, and (iii) word2vec word embeddings along with a DL classifier. The two BoW-based

TABLE II
EVALUATION RESULTS OF THE OVERALL ANALYSIS

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F ₁ -score (%)	F ₂ -score (%)
BoW	89.7	96.7	59.0	73.2	63.9
TF-IDF	90.2	98.3	60.0	74.5	65.0
Word2vec	85.2	69.3	68.0	68.7	68.2
BERT	93.0	90.8	79.0	84.5	81.1
GPT-2	87.3	77.0	67.0	71.6	68.8
T5	91.1	88.9	72.0	79.5	74.8
CodeBERT	90.9	78.1	86.1	81.9	84.3
CodeGPT-2	88.7	81.1	68.9	74.5	71.1
CodeT5	90.9	86.0	74.0	79.5	76.1

methods used an ML classifier to classify files as vulnerable or non-vulnerable. The best classifier proved to be the Random Forest model. On the other hand, the word2vec embeddings were fed to an LSTM model, which has demonstrated the best results among non-Transformer models in the VP literature [25]. The results in Table II show that:

All examined LLMs manage to achieve superior results compared to BoW, TF-IDF, and word2vec, highlighting the important benefit gained by leveraging transfer learning in VP.

Furthermore, we can notice that all the three pre-trained on-code LLMs manage to outperform their NLP variants. In particular, CodeBERT surpasses BERT by 3.2% in terms of F₂-score, while both CodeGPT-2 and CodeT5 outperform GPT-2 and T5 by 2.3%. This observation highlights the importance of the data utilized in the pre-training process. The fact that CodeBERT, CodeGPT-2, and CodeT5 proved to be the superior models can be attributed to the nature of their pre-training knowledge. Hence, we can argue that:

In the VP downstream task, which is a source code-related task, it is beneficial to use models that have prior knowledge of programming languages.

In addition, as can be seen in Table II, the highest F₂-score (i.e., 84.3%), which is in bold, is achieved by CodeBERT but the second highest is achieved by BERT instead of CodeT5 or CodeGPT-2. In other words, BERT surpasses clearly not only the other two NLP models but also their code-aware variants. This finding suggests that Transformer-based models that leverage the encoder part of the Transformer architecture (e.g., BERT and CodeBERT) may be more capable of predicting vulnerable software components as opposed to models that include only the decoder (e.g., GPT-2 and CodeGPT-2) or the whole Transformer architecture (e.g., T5 and CodeT5), and therefore, a more detailed analysis can be conducted in this direction. Concisely, we noticed that:

The encoder-only BERT and CodeBERT outperformed the decoder-only GPT-2 and CodeGPT-2 as well as the encoder-decoder T5 and CodeT5.

We also investigated if there is any correlation between the performance of the models and their size. Specifically, we examined if the F₂-scores (see Table II) of our six fine-tuned models are correlated with the number of trainable param-

TABLE III
NUMBER OF TRAINABLE PARAMETERS OF THE FINE-TUNED MODELS

Model	Number of Trainable Parameters
BERT	109,485,314
GPT-2	124,443,648
T5	223,475,714
CodeBERT	124,648,706
CodeGPT-2	124,248,576
CodeT5	223,475,714

eters of these models, which is presented in Table III. For this purpose, we employed the Spearman’s rank coefficient. Spearman’s correlation is a non-parametric statistical measure used to determine whether there is a monotonic relationship between two ordinal variables, including its strength and direction. By using the “stats” module of the “SciPy” library, we computed the Spearman correlation coefficient equal to 0.058. We judged the strength of the correlation utilizing the guidelines provided by Cohen et al. [37]. Cohen et al. state that a correlation of less than 0.3 is weak, between 0.3 and 0.5 is moderate, and greater than 0.5 is strong. A positive correlation that is close to one generally indicates that the studied rankings are nearly identical. Therefore, a Spearman coefficient equal to 0.058 indicates a very weak positive correlation between the F₂-scores and the number of trainable parameters of the models. Hence, we can argue that:

The efficiency (expressed by the F₂-score) of the examined LLMs fine-tuned in vulnerability prediction does not depend significantly on the number of trainable parameters and, therefore, on the size of the models.

Another interesting observation from our analysis concerns the perception time of LLM-based VPMs during the execution phase. For instance, the CodeBERT-based VPM, which performed best in our analysis (see Table II), required 12.8 minutes for fine-tuning in this dataset but only 9 milliseconds to classify a new sample. This short perception time underscores their potential as co-pilots in software development, allowing developers to quickly address vulnerabilities without disrupting their workflow.

Finally, a remark on the limitations and threats to validity of our approach is essential. Our conclusions may face data validity threats, as they are based on a specific dataset of open-source Python code. Broader studies on diverse datasets and

languages would help generalize our findings. Additionally, not all hyperparameter combinations were explored, posing a potential threat to internal validity, though we mitigated this with comprehensive tuning. Moreover, an external validity threat lies in using models from Hugging Face Transformers library, which may differ slightly from the original publications due to pre-training variations. Lastly, the hallucinatory capacity of LLMs could lead to FP by mistakenly associating non-vulnerable patterns with vulnerabilities, but this risk is minimized by our carefully designed fine-tuning process using a curated dataset of real vulnerabilities.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper aimed to compare the VP capabilities of several Transformer-based pre-trained models, including BERT, CodeBERT, GPT-2, CodeGPT-2, T5, and CodeT5. The results showed that code-specific LLMs outperformed their natural language variants, with the encoder part of the Transformer proving particularly effective. Moreover, we did not notice a significant effect of the LLMs size. Finally, all LLM-based VP solutions outperformed traditional text mining methods.

Future work includes the investigation of whether prior knowledge of natural language is useful for vulnerability prediction, or whether pre-training models exclusively on source code will be proved a better approach. In addition, future research endeavors may examine explainability techniques to reduce the level of code granularity to line or function level.

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